

ADVANCING TECHNICAL EDUCATION WITH ESSENTIAL FOREIGN LANGUAGE MASTERY

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Abstract: This article examines the increasing necessity for foreign language proficiency among graduates in the modern, globalized world, with a specific focus on English due to its dominant role in global affairs. The discussion highlights the dual necessity of understanding primary resources in their original language for academic and professional purposes, and the requirement for effective communication in an internationally interconnected market.

Key words: foreign language education, English proficiency, global competence, technical higher education, innovative teaching methods, professional communication skills, curriculum development.

In today's globalized world, the demand for modern graduates to be not only well-educated but also proficient in professional competencies is higher than ever. Among these competencies, mastery of a foreign language stands out as particularly essential. This increasing importance can be attributed to several key factors. Firstly, there is a pressing need for scholars and professionals to directly access primary sources in their original languages [1]. This enables timely and accurate engagement with the latest advancements in global science and technology, as well as with evolving socio-economic trends worldwide. Secondly, as global trade expands and cultural and social exchanges between countries increase, so does the requirement for individuals to communicate across cultures. These interactions necessitate a proficiency in foreign languages. Currently, English dominates as the primary foreign language due to its widespread use in global commerce, science, and cultural

exchanges. The prominence of English-speaking nations in global affairs has secured English a leading position in international communication. In almost every sector of the global economy, English serves as the preferred language of communication.

With Uzbekistan’s increasing integration into international frameworks and organizations, proficiency in English is becoming vital. The significance of English is reflected in the evolving content and methodologies of language education, particularly within the sphere of technical higher education. This shift necessitates not only changes in the organization of educational processes but also in the specific content of foreign language courses [2].

Considering the specific needs of technical higher education institutions, it is apparent that merely knowing a foreign language is insufficient for graduates to effectively respond to the rapid changes in the world of science and technology. Specialized language training - such as business English, technical English, and English for specific professional fields - is crucial for preparing students as competent professionals.

In technical higher education, teaching methodologies can broadly be divided into two categories:

Information and communication technologies, which include computer programs, multimedia resources, electronic textbooks, and various online tools such as dictionaries and digital libraries.

Person-centered technologies, which focus on adaptive learning strategies such as multi-level training, project-based learning, problem-solving exercises, collaborative learning, and health-oriented education [3].

These innovative teaching methods aim to develop students who are not only knowledgeable but also capable of independent thought, creative problem-solving, and continuous self-learning. A modern English language curriculum in technical institutions should therefore avoid repetitive patterns and instead strive to engage, motivate, and intellectually challenge students to foster their personal and professional development [4].

This approach to teaching English in technical higher education institutions emphasizes the active involvement of students in applying their language skills practically. Encouraging independent cognitive and communicative activities in English remains a core objective for achieving proficiency [5].

In conclusion, the integration of advanced educational technologies and methodologies aimed at fostering active, independent learning is crucial for preparing future engineers and professionals who are proficient in English and capable of navigating the international landscape effectively.

References:

1. Gapparov, A. J. "Young Learners and Their Language Learning Ability." (2022).
2. Zhabborovich, Gapparov Abduljalil. "AN INTEGRATED MODEL OF TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE AND THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE INFORMATION EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT OF SCHOOLS." *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol 8.3* (2020).
3. Janikulovna, D. S., Jabbarovich, G. A., Abdumuratovich, K. S., & Bakhridinovich, J. I. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERCULTURAL INTERACTION IN THE STUDY OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Проблемы педагогики*, (5 (56)), 36-38.
4. Sh, Kuziev. "The ways of developing discourse competence in non-linguistic faculties." *The academy of Ma'mun in Kharezm* 5 (2020).
5. Kuziev, S. H., and S. Rahmonova. "Distance learning and technology- the future of national education." *Foreign languages in Uzbekistan* 1 (2018): 20.
6. Kuziev, Shavkat, and Mukhlisa Kuzieva. "SOCIAL NETWORKS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH." *Talqin va tadqiqotlar* 1.9 (2023).
7. Кузиев, Шавкат Абдумуратович. "ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ВОСИТАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ." *Scientific Impulse* 1.5 (2022): 1641-1643.

8. Abdumuratovich, Kuziev Shavkat. "MODERN METHODS AND TIPS OF LEARNING ENGLISH." *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH* 6.3 (2023): 58-60.
9. Kuziev, Shavkat Abdumuratovich. "THE ROLE OF AUDIENCE AND CONTEXT IN THE SPEECH." *Наука и образование: сохраняя прошлое, создаём будущее*. 2017.
10. Abdumuratovich, Kuziev Shavkat. "HEI POLICIES ON AI USE." *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE*. Vol. 2. No. 19. 2023.
11. Abdumuratovich, Kuziyev Shavkat. "AI IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS." *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*. 2023.
12. Abdumuratovich, Kuziev Shavkat. "TEACHING WRITING THROUGH THE USE OF ChatGPT." *PEDAGOG* 7.4 (2024): 61-63.
13. Kuziev, Shavkat. "POLICY FRAMEWORKS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES FOR AI INTEGRATION: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS." *Ilm-fan va ta'lim* 5 (20) (2024).
14. Abdumuratovich, Kuziev Shavkat. "COMPARISON OF AI POLICY." *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI* 7.4 (2024): 204-206.